

37th EFFoST International Conference 2023

*Sustainable Food and Industry 4.0:
Towards the 2030 Agenda*

6-8 November 2023 | Valencia, Spain

Organised by:

UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA

Instituto de Agroquímica y Tecnología de Alimentos

EXCELENCIA SEVERO OCHOA

CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

Hosted by:

EFFoST

6-8 November
Valencia, Spain

★ ★ 2023

INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE

www.fffostconference.com

Abstract book

Accepted Posters

P1.1.048

Towards the development and application of green extraction technologies: the concept of EXCEL4MED

Valdramidis V¹, Psakis G², Dimitros I¹, Giannoglou M³, Dasenaki M¹, Gatt R², Katsaros G³

¹University Of Athens, ²University of Malta, ³ELGO DIMITRA

Aim

The excellence hub EXCEL4MED is an initiative to strengthen Mediterranean innovation excellence in innovation ecosystems focusing on the production of nutritious food products and the valorization of food industrial side-streams. The project aims at identifying high-impact strategies and establish lines of resilience for producers, processors, consumers and policymakers. Overall, EXCEL4MED will offer an adaptive capability in the Mediterranean supply chain preparing for novel waste valorisation strategies, production of added value fruit products following a holistic commerce, and the implementation of green innovative technological methodologies. EXCEL4MED will develop and demonstrate the solution in Mediterranean high-value perishable food supply chains: pomegranate and citrus fruits.

Method

EXCEL4MED will develop a conceptual design and pre-planning for pilots and demonstrators of electrochemical and sonochemical technologies in the food industry. Proof of concepts and scale-up validation assessments will be developed for the pomegranate and citrus food chains. This will be achieved by consolidating academic business linkages and providing evidence for strategy building and investment. Application of green processes for improved extraction of bioactive compounds from pomegranate seed oil, citrus and pomegranate pericarps will be carried out

Results

Experimental studies are currently carried out to characterize the bioactive compounds of different pomegranate and citrus varieties. The effectiveness of Electric Field (PEF), Ultrasound (US) and Hydrodynamic Cavitation (HC) as pre-treatments are compared to standard methods e.g., using enzymes, as well as to hybrid treatments. The bioactive compounds are extracted using standard methods, following characterization and quantification. The antioxidant capacity of the bioactive substances are determined through the radical scavenging method (DPPH), the Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power Assay (FRAP) and the ABTS radical-cation reduction test. The best-performed treatment conditions will be identified and selected.

Conclusion:

EXCEL4MED will create 4 pilot projects in Malta and Greece; 3 on added value products and 1 on valorisation. At the end of the project, partners will provide the pilot regions specific recommendations for a joint policy in food processing, taking into consideration already identified innovation strategies for smart specialization.